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TNA Services Management Plan

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List of Abbreviations

BoD	Board of Directors
FAIR	FAIR principles of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability
FTE	Full Time Equivalent
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GenA	General Assembly
GLAM	Sector that includes Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museums
HQ	Head Quarter
ITSERR	Italian National Project "Italian Strengthening of the ESFRI RI RESILIENCE"
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
OA	Open Access
PP	Preparatory Phase
ReReS	EU Project "Research Infrastructure on Religious Studies" 2018-2021
RI	Research Infrastructure

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TNA	Transnational Access
ToC	Table of Contents
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

This deliverable is part of the set of deliverables produced by Work Package 2 that together describe and prepare for the current and future RESILIENCE services. The TNA Management Plan concerns a specific RESILIENCE Service: Transnational Access. Accessibility has been flagged by RESILIENCE as a key need of researchers in its user research.¹ According to the Grant Agreement of the RESILIENCE PP it should describe the “[...] criteria of excellence for TNA hosts and users, their rights and duties within the program, quality monitoring procedures and responsibilities (incl. Peer Review Committee), and efficient information providing and research enhancing workflows”.² This will be followed by D2.12 TNA Management Report, which will report on the prototyping and activities conducted by RESILIENCE TNA during the RESILIENCE Preparatory Phase (2022-2026).

1.1 Aim of the TNA Management Plan

Within the Service Strategy, TNA will function as a core service, to be fully coordinated and managed by the future RESILIENCE headquarters.³ The TNA Management Plan thus subscribes to the guiding principles of a RESILIENCE Service, namely that it strives to ensure “[...] expertise, excellence, FAIR, sustainability, transparency, and a clear description of the service[...]”.⁴ It is chiefly informed by three sets of previous experiences and resources:

- a) The RESILIENCE TNA programme conducted during the RESILIENCE PP, which provides crucial insight into the current challenges and opportunities;
- b) Research on other transnational programs and activities within the humanities, ESFRI, and other relevant initiatives, to provide background and insight;
- c) The reports and experiences of RelReS (Research Infrastructure on Religious Studies), which ran a successful fully funded TNA programme from 2018-2021. The latter is important for its comparison with the current in-kind programme, as well as providing the blueprint for the RESILIENCE TNA Programme.

The programme currently operates at a technological readiness level of 6: “A functional version of the product working on a realistic environment able to draw conclusions on the technical and operational capabilities of the product.”⁵ It is in the validating phase of prototyping, where it is functioning in its targeted environment, but is missing a few components that can only be implemented in the next phase, which prevents it from being fully operational.

¹ Cf. the List of prioritised User Requirements in [RESILIENCE WP3 D3.5 User-Stories-Catalogue-1st-Batch](#), chap. 4.1, 4.2.

² Grant Agreement-101079792-RESILIENCE PPP, p. 17-18.

³ [RESILIENCE WP2 D2.1 Services Preparation and Implementation Strategy](#)(version 03.00 July 2025), p. 20.

⁴ [RESILIENCE WP2 D2.1 Services Preparation and Implementation Strategy](#), p 10. For a more thorough outline of these principles, see p. 10-14.

⁵ See <https://horizoneuropencportal.eu/store/trl-assessment> for an overview of the TRLs and examples.

During the RelReS phase of TNA, 87 users from 23 countries completed their TNA project, spending a total of 180 access weeks. Applicants conducted research within historical Religious Studies at one of the fourteen available TNA Hosts, at this phase still only consisting of libraries and archives. By July 2021, 19 scholars had published research that been (partially or wholly) produced as a result of a RelReS scholarship in scientific journals, books or as part of dissertations, 49 more were in preparation (in the peer review process or in print), and 10 presentations were given at conferences. Publications in Open Access were collected for the RelReS website until July 2021 and can still be accessed here: <https://reires.eu/online-workshop-materials/publications/>.

Given this success and the excellent reputation of the programme, it was decided at the beginning of the RESILIENCE Preparatory Phase to continue running an in-kind, limited version of the programme. It is therefore not a funded programme: the agreements made with TNA Hosts are voluntary and temporary, and do not include any kind of financial or legal obligations; nor do TNA Fellows receive any kind of scholarship unless a TNA Host was able and willing to provide those funds independently. This construction allowed us to profit from the network and experience of RelReS and thereby ensure that as little expertise and momentum was lost. In doing so we hope to build a tried and tested bridge towards the next phase of the TNA Programme within RESILIENCE.

The Detailed Organization Plan contains a more in-depth list of tasks for T2.6 TNA.⁶ With regard to managing the current version of the TNA programme, the sub-tasks assigned to T2.6 Preparing Trans-National Access services activities should be read iteratively: each year, we prepare TNA activities, analyse the cost and resources available and determine the scope of the programme for that year. This is followed by running the TNA Call and Programme and evaluation and feedback of the programme, both of which together take up most of the effort, as acknowledged by the effort division in the DOP. This process was then used as the basis for this final deliverable, allowing us to present a truly tested and thriving TNA Service.

This deliverable will therefore outline the TNA Programme from a management perspective once RESILIENCE transitions towards an ERIC. While it was run as an in-kind service during the PP, this plan assumes funded scholarships within the context of the RESILIENCE Implementation Phase. The remainder of Chapter 1 will describe the current *raison d'être* and describe the main aims of the TNA Programme. Chapter 2 will outline governance and financial management of the programme, while Chapter 3 describes the workflows and procedures related to the TNA Fellows and TNA Hosts. Chapter 4 outlines some key long-term strategies, while Chapter five concludes with a short description on the communication, dissemination, and impact of the future TNA Programme. All the documents related to the TNA Programme cited in the deliverable can be found in the annexes.

1.2 Why a TNA Programme for the Study of Religion?

In its current phase (2022-2026) RESILIENCE is conducting research into the needs of its future users: researchers, scholars, librarians, archivists, and other actors for whom advanced and excellent knowledge of religion is necessary to execute their professional responsibilities. As part of that research, WP 3, together

⁶ See [RESILIENCE WP6 D6.3 DetailedOrganisationalPlan](#).

with WP₂ (led by KU Leuven) and WP₄ (led by the Theological University Apeldoorn), designed a model of two-day “user requirement” workshops aimed at discovering and mapping the needs of future RESILIENCE users.⁷ While the full results of these workshops have yet to be published, interim results have shown the top two factors cited as the most common need amongst researchers were access (chiefly related to accessing academic literature), and networking, with the caveat that both require consistent funding that is often not available.⁸

As one of the few truly interdisciplinary academic fields of study, the study of religion possesses a vast range of knowledge loci, leading to diverse sets of data, all of which are subject to their own limitations and specifications. They extend across time (historical and contemporary data), context (culture, geography, language, religion), and are multimodal, ranging from texts to numbers to images to physical and material data. The study of religion thus suffers from both an abundance and scarcity of sources, as observed by Lincoln A. Mullen in his article “The Making of America’s Public Bible: Computational Text Analysis for Religious History”:

“However partial they may be, the archival and the printed record is vast. Despite the labours of librarians and archivists, our sources are inadequately catalogued and indexed. For even the most narrowly targeted scholarly question, the sources available outstrip the historian’s time and ability to read.”⁹

While it can be expected that digitization could help this issue, the opposite seems to be the case. Digitization exacerbates both the scarcity of undigitized sources and the abundance of digitized sources: the huge number of databases containing digitized collections of primary sources can feel overwhelming to researchers, while at the same time, digitized sources are nowhere near a full representation of the past. However, their accessibility leads researchers “[...] to use those sources rather than other sources which are available in the archive but remain undigitized.”¹⁰

This means that in-person, physical access to sources is by no means an outdated necessity for researchers; indeed, it is the combination of digital and physical access to data that is and will remain essential for comprehensive multidisciplinary and multilingual research in the study of religion. Providing only digital data and tools excludes sources as well as specific contents, expressive forms and particular disciplines of the study of religion and does not enable holistic research. Via its Transnational Access Programme, RESILIENCE aims to build this bridge between physical and digital access.

The RESILIENCE TNA Programme offers physical and virtual (as opposed to digital: virtual implies those sources that are only available via onsite computer and/or networking access) across national borders to the most significant tools and sources in those disciplines related to the study of religion. TNA offers support

⁷ Workshop Proceedings – 1st Batch, D3.1 (2024), p. 6-9. See [RESILIENCE WP3_D3.1_WorkshopProceedings1](#).

⁸ User Stories Catalogue - 1st Batch, D3.5 (2023), p. 18-19. See [RESILIENCE WP3_D3.5_User-Stories-Catalogue-1st-Batch](#).

⁹ Lincoln A. Mullen: The Making of America’s Public Bible: Computational Text Analysis for Religious History, in: Digital Humanities and Research Methods in Religious Studies: An Introduction, ed. by Christopher D. Cantwell and Kristian Petersen (Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter, 2021), p. 31-52:
<https://doi-org.kuleuven.e-bronnen.be/10.1515/9783110573022-003>.

¹⁰ Lincoln A. Mullen, The Making of America’s Public Bible, p. 38.

and expertise for research stays at a number of European institutions and libraries that possess unique collections and expertise on the study of religion as a whole. This includes, but is not limited to, the sources and expertise needed to conduct research on the contemporary and historical study of the world's major and minor religions, as well as new religious movements, secularization and non-religious worldviews, indigenous religions across the globe, and more. Its aim is to facilitate and foster easy access to sources, resources, expertise and services for researchers in The study of religion, while ensuring an efficient access workflow and a single-entry point via the RESILIENCE homepage and central helpdesk.

TNA therefore aims to answer to the need of scholars to have direct and effective access to sources located in different countries. Often, such collections have not been digitized, and access to these sources is restricted. In order to provide excellence-driven access to its physical resources, TNA partners offer assistance to researchers seeking to conduct a research visit at one of the host facilities offering this service. The goal of TNA therefore is to facilitate direct and effective access for scholars to the objects of their research: TNA hosts grant access to their collections of manuscripts, rare books, documents and materials, and provide instructions to effectively make use of their collections. This allows scholars to dedicate as much of their research stay to actual research as possible, and allows them to make use of the available local expertise as efficiently as possible.

In addition to access to sources, RESILIENCE also aims to improve the networking capital of its TNA Fellows, by matching TNA scholars with relevant experts who can provide tailored expertise. This offer is thus combines access to data of major European research institutions together with access to a vast network of experts for the study of religion. RESILIENCE therefore aims to not only attract academic institutions, but also policy makers, religious institutions, and independent research institutes. In short, the role of the RESILIENCE TNA program is fundamentally a facilitating one, benefiting both host and recipient, and supported by RESILIENCE's excellent professional network.

While many exchange and visiting scholar programmes exist, the specific approach of TNA has some unique aspects. Both the TNA programme conducted in the RelReS and Preparatory Phase projects have shown that unlike for example the Erasmus Programmes it draws early career researchers, starting with PhD candidates, and also including post-doctoral scholars, and early tenure track researchers. Its personalized and tailored approach is also something which makes it stand out amongst the larger EU exchange programmes. The closest counterpart is the similar set-up of DARIAH's recent launch of [ATRIUM](#), specifically its Transnational Access Scheme Grants – Individual Access for the Digital Humanities. Here there is a similar emphasis on a tailored approach, and a similar audience. The key difference is that ATRIUM TNA Hosts focus on the Digital Humanities, whereas RESILIENCE leverages its expertise on the study of religion across all disciplines.

1.3 RESILIENCE TNA Programme 2022-2025

During the PP, RESILIENCE TNA ran a limited TNA Programme. While the D2.12 TNA Management Report will analyse and report on the full results of that programme, it is worthwhile to highlight a few key insights and recommendations on the current status quo. In October 2023 an evaluation was held of the first year,

which resulted in a confidential Strategy Report for 2023-2026, as well as a number of key recommendations.

The key difference in the two versions of the programme is that the prototyping programme was an unfunded, fully in-kind programme, whereas the future RESILIENCE TNA Programme will be funded. Management of the TNA Host Network was part of the tasks of WP2 Services, with KU Leuven as lead. WP2 contains four main work units: Data (responsible for the data management within the current consortium and future RI), Training (responsible for developing a training programme), and IT (responsible for outlining IT Services and support for the future RI), one of which is Transnational Access. A total of 798 effort days were dedicated to prototyping the future TNA Programme, divided amongst the consortium partners. 52% of that effort is divided amongst KU Leuven and INFAL. All partners received 30 effort days for the TNA task, which are being used to run a prototype of the TNA programme.

Currently RESILIENCE TNA has signed a bilateral agreement until 2026 with of 20 individual TNA hosts: FSCIRE (Bologna, IT), KU Leuven (BE), Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski"(BG), Theological University of Apeldoorn (NL), University of Münster (DE), University of Sarajevo (BIH), Volos Academy for Theological Studies (GR), Bar-Ilan University (Ramat Gan, IL), Bektashi World Center (Tirana, AL), CIRCSE (Milan, IT), mikado Library (Aachen, DE)¹¹, New Georgian University (Poti, GE), University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Theology (SI), J.A. Comenius Museum (Uherský Brod, CZ), "Saint Epiphanius" Cultural Academy (CY), Archivio Generale Arcivescovile di Bologna, AAB (Bologna, IT), Bibliothèque nationale et universitaire de Strasbourg (FR), École Pratique des Hautes Études (FR), Europäische Melanchthon-Akademie Bretten (DE), and the University of Warsaw (PL).¹²

In addition to the bilateral agreements, RESILIENCE TNA has also signed an agreement until October 2025 with [ITSERR TNA](#) and its five Italian hosts that are part of the ITSERR consortium (Italian Strengthening of the ESFRI RI RESILIENCE, funded by NextGenerationEU): Institute of Information Science and Technologies "Alessandro Faedo" (ISTI-CNR) in Pisa, affiliated to the National Research Council (CNR), Università di Modena e Reggio Emilia (UniMORE), Università di Napoli "l'Orientale" (UniOr), Università degli Studi di Palermo (UniPa), Università di Torino (UniTo).¹³ This brings the total of individual TNA Hosts to 25.

Given that there were not financial or legal obligations, the agreement between RESILIENCE TNA and the TNA Host were framed in the context of a temporary Memorandum of Understanding.¹⁴ The MoU lists the mandatory in-kind services as determined by RESILIENCE TNA: free access to collections, provide a

¹¹ The mikado Library had to withdraw from the RESILIENCE TNA programme as of 31 December 2024, because it was closed to the public and staff numbers were reduced accordingly. The one outstanding TNA stay can still be carried out after this date with full access to the library and guidance, but has not yet been started due to scheduling difficulties on the part of the TNA fellow.

¹² For descriptions of RESILIENCE TNA Hosts with their benefits, collections and expertise, see here: <https://www.resilience-ri.eu/cfa-tna/>

¹³ ITSERR (Italian Strengthening of the ESFRI RI RESILIENCE) is an interdisciplinary and distributed Research Infrastructure for Religious Studies whose main purpose is to strengthen the RESILIENCE RI in its preparatory phase, through its national institutional dimension, scientific positioning, technical development, and public perception. See <https://www.itserr.it/> for more information.

¹⁴ This version of the MoU will be included in D2.12 TNA Management Report. The MoU included in the Annex (7.1) is intended for the next phase of RESILIENCE.

workplace, aid in navigating collections, and arranging a meet up with at least one on-site expert. Additional in-kind services offered voluntarily by hosts included paid or reduced accommodation, public transportation discounts, airport transfers, hospitality services, access to digital services, free printing, scanning, and copying.

The final TNA Call of this phase took place between March 15 – May 1, 2025. In total, RESILIENCE TNA has received 93 TNA Fellow Applications, 71 of which were accepted. Of those, a total of 44 research stays have already been completed, and 15 will still be completed in the upcoming academic year (this includes three fellows who postponed their research stay). Twelve TNA Fellows had to postpone or cancel their research stay: four cited geopolitical tensions in Israel-Gaza, five a lack of funding and/or a funded opportunity arose, one cited paternity leave, another cancellation was due to the fact that it was impossible to find a date within the short period of time available for an ITSERR-funded TNA stay, in addition to other professional and family commitments. A more complete report of all these stays will be included in D2.12 TNA Management Report.

The current version of RESILIENCE TNA requires three roles, which can be fulfilled by the same person: programme officer, operational officer, and communications officer. Within the PP the Programme Officer role was fulfilled by the WU Research Services Lead KU Leuven (118 effort days), while the Operational Officer was fulfilled by WU Research Services Team Member INFAl (300 effort days). Communications was conducted by both INFAl and the WP CDE Team Lead TUA (60 effort days).

Very few aspects of these roles were automatized, leading to a relatively high personnel investment. Therefore, in May 2024 planning began for a RESILIENCE TNA Portal: an online platform for both TNA Hosts and TNA Fellows that would be embedded within the RESILIENCE RI. A prototype of this platform was developed by ITSERR, and will be further developed in the next phase of RESILIENCE. Not only will it provide a more efficient overview of the available hosts and resources, it will also partially automate the application and evaluation processes within the programme.

1.4 Key Experiences and Recommendations 2022-2025

The key recommendations are drawn from two TNA Programmes that ran during 2022-2025: RESILIENCE TNA and ITSERR TNA.

1.4.1 RESILIENCE TNA

During the implementation phase, two different types of TNA grants are foreseen for the implementation phase: individual mobility grants and team mobility grants. The individual mobility grants have been tested during both the ReIReS and RESILIENCE PP phase; during both phases the interest in the programme was consistent, diverse, and surprisingly popular, especially given the lack of funding during the PP phase. Physical access to sources is clearly still not only necessary and fundamental for researchers studying religion, it is also not sufficiently available or easy to access. This is also not likely to change within the field, given the immense cost and effort associated with digitizing collections, and effort that is simply not possible for the small institutions contributing to the study of religion.

The TNA Management Report (D2.11) which will be published in 2026 will contain a full analysis of the TNA Programme during the RESILIENCE Preparatory Phase. However, the evaluations and experiences gained already reveal the following general challenges and recommendations:

1. In general **reviews by the TNA Fellows were very positive**, with high ratings across the board. Key features that were appreciated the most by Fellows that should be maintained were: (1) The emphasis on personal contact and practical help in preparing the visit; (2) The networking opportunities, especially the chance to meet up with a local expert; (3) The chance to share research with local researchers.
2. **The geographic diversity of the programme**, both in terms of TNA Hosts and TNA Fellows, was quite astounding. In the first two years twenty-four countries were represented amongst the successful TNA Applicants. This diversity should be maintained and encouraged as much as possible.
3. **Lack of funding** was highlighted as a key issue for TNA Fellows, both as a reason for cancelling visits and as a criticism of the program in evaluations.
4. **The personnel effort required** to run this programme successfully is very high. Key bottle necks our team faced were the following:
 - a. Constant follow-up required with both TNA Hosts and TNA Fellows for updates on TNA stays, requests for evaluations and reports, and updates on publications;
 - b. Difficult to monitor and meet onsite challenges faced during the TNA stays by both TNA Hosts and Fellows;
 - c. Difficult to ensure that both TNA Hosts and Fellows aligned with the terms and conditions of the programme.
5. Related to (4), **upscaling the programme is challenging** since it exponentially increases the staff effort required to run this version of the programme. This was therefore slowed down in the second half of the preparatory phase, and completely halted from the summer of 2025 onwards. Institutes could still join the TNA Hosting Network, but not as active TNA Hosts.

1.4.2 ITSERR TNA

Between October 2023 and October 2025 ITSERR TNA was able to run a fully funded [TNA Programme](#) that could experiment with a few key factors. The first is that it essentially functioned as a future distributed RI: five Italian institutes were connected to the ITSERR TNA Programme, led by the University of Palermo, which functioned as a national node. The programme was run by the ITSERR TNA Coordinator, who thus functioned as the National TNA Coordinator, but the TNA Calls were embedded within the RESILIENCE TNA communication and administration structures.

Italy was thus able to test-run a TNA national node use case, which led to a number of key insights that are relevant for the future TNA Programme. The first is that ITSERR was reliant on travel agencies to facilitate

their travel and accommodation bookings, which complicated the financial workflows immensely. Any changes needed to be communicated via a third party, and the reimbursement process was very complex and stressful for TNA Fellows. The recommendation that came from this was to **simplify financial procedures** where possible. The future grant system does this in two ways: grant money will not be disbursed by individual institutes, but from RESILIENCE, bypassing national and institutional financial complexities. Secondly, we chose to adopt the grant system outlined in section 2.2.1, where TNA Fellows book travel and accommodation themselves, and receive the living stipend as a lump sum on their arrival day. In this way we hope to increase the accessibility and efficiency of the financial management for both TNA Management and TNA Fellows.

The second key insight is the **importance of creating a national community**. While ITSERR was able to run a skeleton national node, the lines of communication between the TNA Coordinator and the TNA Hosts were not always clear or streamlined, leading to delays in planning TNA visits for accepted TNA Fellows. The key thing that was missing was the embedding of the TNA Programme within a larger national infrastructure. Each national node will have effort and budget for national events, communication, and dissemination – and this is also a crucial aspect for increasing the sense of community for the TNA Hosting Network in each country.

In addition to these trends, two key areas of growth were identified, leading to two recommendations. The first concerns the **automatization of workflows** to reduce personnel costs and increase efficiency and ease of access to the programme. Any exchange programme requires a lot of human effort, but there are ways to increase the efficiency of specific workflows and procedures. The recommendation was to develop a dedicated platform on the RESILIENCE marketplace, to be used by RESILIENCE members, TNA Hosts, and TNA Fellows. Since October 2024 ITSERR has devoted effort and funding toward developing a prototype for such a TNA Portal, which will become a part of the future RESILIENCE marketplace (see section 4.1 on the TNA Portal).

The second focuses on the controlled **expansion of the TNA Hosting Network** to increase the quality and diversity of the hosts for TNA Fellows. The WU Research Service recommended a focus on the following areas: religious diversity, expansion in Eastern Europe (aligning with WP4), Southwestern Europe and Northern Europe, and to explore expansion into the UK, the US, and MENA. MENA is currently not an option due to the regional instability, but should be included in the long-term strategy. This expansion does not need to be conducted in tandem with the growth of the RI as a whole, since institutions can become a TNA Host without joining the consortium or future ERIC.

TNA team mobility was envisioned in the context ITSERR, but this could not be implemented. In spite of an open TNA Team Call, ITSERR did not receive any team application, so there is not enough information available on the management of such fellowships for inclusion in this deliverable.

ITSERR was able to test a second type of individual mobility grant was also tested during the final two TNA Calls in 2025, namely the **staff exchanges**. The aim of these TNA exchanges is not primarily conducting research or accessing sources, but an exchange of staff and/or project expertise. Three Italian TNA Fellows took part in this prototype. The conclusion of these case studies is as follows: it is relatively easy to incorporate these kinds of individual mobility, and the same procedures and terms and conditions can be followed. However, it is important that a separate application form is developed to ensure that the TNA

Fellows can be set up with onsite experts – this part of the TNA experience is even more crucial for a staff exchange than for a research fellowship. In addition to this, not all TNA Hosts will be able or wish to accommodate a staff exchange, since it requires accessibility to different departments than the research fellowships. Staff exchanges should therefore be discussed separately during the onboarding phase of new TNA Hosts. For the same reason it is not mandatory for TNA Hosts to participate in this kind of TNA mobility, and TNA Hosts can update their TNA offer to include staff exchanges if they wish.

In the two chapters that follow, the above recommendations, as well as previous experiences with TNA will inform the TNA Programme, describing governance and financial management, the required procedures and workflows on the management of TNA Fellows and Hosts, and the initial plans for a TNA Portal to facilitate these.

1.5 Collaboration with EHRI-EU

In the spring of 2025 we started talks with [EHRI-EU](#), the European Holocaust Research Infrastructure, to align our respective TNA Programmes where possible, with the aim of future collaboration and possible integration. Our respective TNA Programmes have a very similar structure and aim, including the following key characteristics:

1. A distributed RI structure with similar services and objectives in their respective fields;
2. TNA Institutes affiliated with the main goal of the RI situated throughout Europe that do need to be a member of the RI;
3. Short TNA stays facilitated locally, notably including a meeting with a local expert;
4. Short-term lumpsum grants for TNA Fellows calibrated to each member state within the TNA Programme;
5. Emphasis on physical access of collections and archives that are not (yet) available online or in open access.

These similarities simplified the collaboration talks, and led to alignment on the following management aspects: the MoU with future TNA Hosts, the TNA Fellow Terms and Conditions, and the financial grant structure for the TNA Fellows. In the future, the aim is for the EHRI-EU Programme to join the RESILIENCE TNA Programme via the TNA Platform: users will be able to access TNA Hosts of both RIs from a single TNA access point.

2 Governance and Financial Management of the TNA Programme

Within the current RESILIENCE timeline, the TNA Programme was managed under the auspices of WP2 Services as a prototype programme. From June 2026 onward RESILIENCE aims to transition into its implementation phase, and with the official RESILIENCE TNA programme will be launched. While the initial intention was for the TNA Programme to start its transition from its current in-kind programme to a funded

fellowship programme in 2026, RESILIENCE will likely devote two more years to the transition towards the implementation phase. The plan outlined below is intended for the future, fully funded TNA Programme as part of the future RESILIENCE ERIC.

2.1 Governance: Roles and Responsibilities

In the next phase RESILIENCE aims to become a distributed research infrastructure, with national nodes contributing to the RESILIENCE ERIC. Most of the programme's activities will be managed within the national nodes, with the exception of a few key financial, legal, and governance responsibilities that, within the current plan, will need to be managed at the EU level. Each national node provides a National Host Officer, and each TNA Host also provides a TNA Coordinator. Finally, the TNA Programme requires a Peer Review Board, which consists of a mix of RESILIENCE and TNA staff. It should be noted that the division between HQ and national node responsibilities outlined below cannot be finalized at this stage of the project, and should therefore not be viewed as definitive. The account below bases itself on input from the PP TNA Programme and the Financial Sustainability Plan.¹⁵

2.1.1 HQ TNA Management Team

HQ staff will contribute to those aspects of the programme that cannot be run at the national level. However, the current HQ staff does not foresee a specific TNA Officer. As such, these responsibilities will be divided according to expertise amongst the current roles foreseen at HQ, including the Communications Officer, Legal and Administration Office, and where necessary the Open Science and Technology Transfer Officer. Key duties concerning the TNA Programme at HQ include the following:

1. Legal and financial management of the TNA Grants
2. Legal and financial management of the TNA Hosting Network
3. Coordinating the Peer Review Board
4. TNA Communication and Dissemination at the EU level
5. Evaluation and monitoring of the programme
6. Maintaining the TNA Portal

The current plan presupposes a steady growth of the TNA Programme, both in terms of TNA Fellows and TNA Hosts. However, we expect that the TNA Portal will offset the required increase in effort so that the personnel hours for TNA can remain steady.

¹⁵ See [RESILIENCE WP1 D1.3 FSP FinancialSustainabilityPlan](#).

2.1.2 TNA National Nodes

National nodes are the national members of the RESILIENCE community. Each national node has a TNA National Host Officer, who coordinates all the TNA Hosts for their country.¹⁶ In accordance with the Service Strategy, the National Host Officer will be responsible (within the limits of the TNA Programme) for:

1. Grow and maintain the national TNA Network
2. Managing all national TNA activities
3. Community outreach and engagement activities
4. Monitoring and evaluation of the programme at the national level
 - a. Define local Key Performance Indicators (KPI) and collect data for monitoring.
 - b. Develop local policies (access policy, data policy ...) and monitor their impact in line with the RESILIENCE RI policies.¹⁷

At the TNA Host institutions themselves, the key contact person is the TNA Coordinator. They ensure physical and administrative access to the institute, and form the main point of contact for the National Host Officer. They should therefore have a senior position in the faculty or institute. In practice it has been shown that researchers at this level rarely have the time for resources for the practical work required to prepare a TNA Visit, which is then often outsourced to junior researchers. It is therefore possible to appoint a TNA Contact Person who can organize the practical aspects of each visit.

2.1.3 Peer Review Board

The Peer Review Board has a twofold role: evaluation TNA Host applications and evaluation TNA Fellow applications. The board forms a continuation of the TNA Host Evaluation Board created for preparation phase, and will consist of seven members:

1. RESILIENCE HQ CDE Representative
2. RESILIENCE HQ M Representative
3. RESILIENCE Advisory Board Member
4. Two active TNA Host Coordinator(s) who are not included in the list above. These members should, where possible, represent a geographic region not included by the members above. They will rotate every two years, and are invited to join by the Access Programme Coordinator .

¹⁶ [RESILIENCE WP1 D1.3 FSP Financial Sustainability Plan](#), p. 19.

¹⁷ [RESILIENCE WP2 D2.1 Services Preparation and Implementation Strategy](#).

5. Two R3/R4 researchers on the study of religion¹⁸: one representing disciplines within the Humanities, and one representing disciplines within the Social Sciences. These members should, where possible, represent a geographic region not included by the members above. They will rotate every two years.

Criteria have been developed for both the TNA Host applications and the TNA Fellow applications (see section 3.1.2 and 3.2.1). The Peer Review Board is responsible for reviewing both sets of applications, and should be prepared to provide feedback on its decisions where required. Contesting procedures for both TNA Fellows and TNA Hosts will be included in the TNA Portal.¹⁹

2.2 Financial Management of the TNA Programme

Given that the current phase of the programme is unfunded, this section describes a future version of the TNA Programme. The financial plan below is primarily based on the [D1.3 Financial Sustainability Plan](#).²⁰ Costs for running a fully implemented TNA Programme can be divided into four categories:

1. TNA Grant Management
2. Personnel and Management costs at RESILIENCE HQ and National Nodes.
3. In-kind contributions provided by the TNA Host, including but not limited to: access to physical and digital TNA Host Infrastructures, meetings with onsite experts, meeting up with experts, workplace, and access to (future) RESILIENCE services and networking events. For some TNA Hosts this can also include (in-kind) accommodation.
4. Internal service: operational costs.

2.2.1 TNA Fellow Grants

The TNA Fellow grants will be managed by the RESILIENCE TNA HQ. The Financial Sustainability Plan includes an initial estimate of TNA Grants for the Implementation phase. For TNA mobility grants for individuals, 20k is foreseen for 20 TNA Fellows per year. For the TNA mobility grants for teams a total of 70k is foreseen per annum, estimated at 5k for each team member, for teams of 3 members, for a duration of about 1 month. The team mobility grants could not be tested in this phase due to the lack of a funded programme.

¹⁸ The EU has identified four unique EU Researcher Career profiles to describe career level. These are categorized according to the level of research independence and influence in the field, with R1 equivalent to a PhD candidate, and R4 equivalent to an international leading scholar in the field. See <https://www.more-4.eu/indicator-tool/career-stages-r1-to-r4>.

¹⁹ As the TNA Portal will not be fully delivered until 2028 at the earliest, this will therefore be developed during the next phase of RESILIENCE.

²⁰ [RESILIENCE WP1 D1.3 FSP FinancialSustainabilityPlan](#), p. 17.

The TNA individual mobility will operate on the principle of: as flexible as possible, as rigid as necessary. What this means in practice is that we do not mandate specific accommodation or flights. The exception to this is if the TNA host offers in-kind accommodation or has an institutional agreement with a third-party on accommodation – in this case the TNA Fellow will be obligated to use this.

Each TNA Fellow will receive the national equivalent of 2000 euros spent in Belgium (this forms the baseline) for their TNA stay. The national equivalent is calculated using the Eurostat European Union Correction Coefficients Index, and will be reviewed annually.²¹ The grant should at minimum cover affordable travel costs, accommodation, (some) living expenses, and (where needed) access to the institution’s collections. TNA Fellows will be encouraged to travel as sustainably as possible. Accommodation can be booked independently by the TNA Fellow, unless the TNA Host has an existing third-party or internal accommodation for visiting scholars. Arrangements via travel agencies are strongly discouraged.

TNA Fellows will sign an agreement with RESILIENCE outlining the grant package and the main duties the TNA Fellow should subscribe to.²² The TNA Fellows make their own travel and accommodation arrangements before they receive the grant. RESILIENCE will then transfer the subsistence grant as soon as the Fellow begins their stay. Reimbursement of travel and accommodation expenses can also be applied for from this moment onwards. In this way we hope to increase the flexibility of the TNA Fellow, who can, for example, choose to spend the grant on cheaper accommodation for a longer stay, or choose a cheaper method of travel to upgrade their accommodation. See Annex (7.5 TNA Fellow Financial Guidance) for an overview of the travel and reimbursement procedures.

2.2.2 Personnel and Management Costs

The table below gives an indication of the main tasks and personnel costs of managing RESILIENCE TNA in the implementation phase. Personnel costs are divided between RESILIENCE HQ and RESILIENCE National Node. RESILIENCE HQ is responsible for all EU-level tasks of the programme, mainly concerning the financial and legal management of the programme, and monitoring and reporting. Most of the TNA activities will be carried out at the national level, which will be managed by the National Host Officer at each national node. Each national node will have a TNA National Host Officer who will manage the national network of TNA Hosts and Fellows.

TNA Personnel		
	Tasks	FTE
RESILIENCE HQ	Initial stages of onboarding new TNA Hosts	0,3 FTE ²³

²¹ Click here for the correction coefficients [within the EU](#), and here for those [outside of the EU](#).

²² See Annex 7.4 TNA Fellow Grant Agreement.

²³ This effort is an estimation based on current experience. It should be clarified at later stages if the HQ will have the financial capability for sustaining it or whether this effort should be distributed.

	Maintaining contact with TNA Hosts	
	Grant administration	
	Monitoring and reporting at RESILIENCE-EU level	
	Updating/maintaining TNA Portal	
	Managing TNA Calls for Applications	
RESILIENCE National Nodes		
National Host Officer	Build and grow the local TNA Network	0,1 FTE per member
	Service Contribution	
	Outreach and engagement	
	Monitoring and evaluation	
	Point of Contact for TNA Fellows	
TNA HOST Partners		
TNA Host Coordinator	Maintaining contact with RESILIENCE	4 hours per month
	Sharing all TNA Communication Updates	
	PR/Networking	
	Membership TNA Peer Review Board	
TNA Contact Person	Contact with TNA Fellow	20 hours per TNA Fellow
	Preparing Visit	
	Running the visit	
	Evaluation of the visit	

Table 1: TNA Personnel

2.2.3 Operational Costs

No operational costs beyond the TNA grants and personnel are foreseen for until the TNA Portal is implemented. Until that time, TNA software maintenance is part of the overall RESILIENCE online

maintenance. Software maintenance for RESILIENCE has been planned at three resources for 0,5 FTE in 2026-2027, 1 FTE in 2028-2031.²⁴ This is intended for the maintenance of ITSERR/RESILIENCE-born tools.

3 Management of TNA Fellows and TNA Hosts

During the PP phase a number of workflows and procedures were developed for the management of both TNA Fellows and TNA Hosts. This chapter describes the operational management of both fellows and hosts, which will primarily take place at the level of the national nodes.

3.1 Management of TNA Fellows

TNA Fellows are expected to conduct original research that results in scientific output, to be published in open access where possible. This includes academic articles, monographs, books and book chapters, conference presentations, science communication, and research data sets. They will meet up with an expert in their topic or field: this meeting should be a minimum of one hour and should focus on the specific research questions of the TNA Fellow. In addition to this, the TNA Fellow should, if possible and desirable, have the opportunity to present their research to onsite peers, via a seminar, or staff meeting, or other format. In short, the TNA Fellow experience is a personalized one, tailored to their specific research and networking needs. The experience in both RelReS and the RESILIENCE PP has shown that the programme attracts early and intermediate career scholars, ranging from the doctoral level to the equivalent of assistant and associate professors.

In the following section, the management of TNA individual mobility is outlined, which includes both the research use case and the staff exchange use case.

3.1.1 TNA Fellow Application Workflow

In the current phase, TNA Fellows apply during the Call for Applications via the RESILIENCE TNA website using an online application form.²⁵ Once the call closes, the applications are sent to the respective hosts. Each TNA Host fills in the TNA Fellow Evaluation Chart for each applicant, and sends this back with their decision. RESILIENCE TNA then emails all the candidates individually with the final decisions, putting the TNA Coordinators of their future TNA Hosts in CC.

With the implementation of a funded TNA programme as well as the TNA Portal, the application process will change. TNA Fellows will apply during each call via the TNA Portal using the application form, which are immediately sent to their respective TNA Hosts. Each TNA Host fills in the TNA Fellow Evaluation Chart (see Annex 7.8) and sends this back to the TNA National Host Coordinator with a recommendation report. The

²⁴ RESILIENCE WP1 D1.3 FSP FinancialSustainabilityPlan, p. 20.

²⁵ See <https://www.resilience-ri.eu/resilience-tna-application-form/> for the current version of the application form. See Annex 7.6 if the application is currently closed.

reason for this is to ensure that the specific materials and expertise requested by the TNA Fellow is actually available at the TNA Host Institute and to filter out candidates that do not meet requirements. The TNA National Host Coordinator collects all the recommendation reports and sends them to the TNA Host Evaluation Board Committee, who make the final decision within the timeframe determined by the call. TNA Fellows are then informed of this decision via the TNA Portal. The TNA Portal is currently still in its prototyping phase, see section 4.1 for some screenshots of the current version.

Should the TNA Portal not be fully ready, the following procedure can be adopted:

Potential TNA Fellows will apply using the application form on the RESILIENCE website. All the application forms are collected every two months and sent to their respective TNA Hosts. Each TNA Host fills in the TNA Fellow Evaluation Chart (see Annex 7.8) and sends this back to the TNA National Host Coordinator with a recommendation report. The TNA National Host Coordinator collects all the recommendation reports and sends them to the TNA Host Evaluation Board Committee, which has one month to make a decision. These are communicated by completing the recommendation reports and sending them back to the TNA National Host Coordinator. While this can be done in a live meeting, it is also possible for each board member to issue his/her vote via email to the programme officer. In this way, prospective TNA Fellows should hear their results within three months of applying. See the figure below for an overview of this process.

Figure 1: TNA Fellow Application Workflow

3.1.2 Criteria of Excellence

The following criteria were developed for TNA Fellow Applications and are available on the current RESILIENCE TNA [website](#). A candidate must obtain a minimum of 50% of the points given for the five main selection and ranking criteria. The yes or no questions function as an extra criterion that can be used to when weighing equal criteria candidates.

Main selection and ranking criteria²⁶

1. Research quality of the proposal **(0–15 points)**.
2. Career profile of the potential user **(0–10 points)**.
3. Potential of the research project **(0–10 points)**.
4. Match between expertise/collections TNA Host and research project **(0-10 points)**.
5. The project has European relevance **(0–5 points)**.

Extra criteria²⁷

1. Equal opportunity: the project is led by, or includes, a female group leader or principle investigator or team member; OR the gender balance within the group members is fulfilled (40/60); OR it includes a specific focus on gender issues **(yes/no)**.
2. Equal opportunity: The project is led by, or benefits, or includes, a differently abled group leader or principal investigator or team member OR it includes a specific focus on disability/trauma issues. **(yes/no)**.
3. The TNA scholar can be considered an early career scholar (Master, PhD, post-doc) **(yes/no)**.
4. The project is proposed by a scholar who has not received a RESILIENCE TNA scholarship before **(yes/no)**.
5. The project requires a strong integration between access to physical collections and the use of digital tools **(yes/no)**.

3.1.3 Gender

To promote gender equality, the evaluation process is aligned with the [Horizon Europe Guidance on Gender Equality Plans](#).

- The Extra criterion 1 uses gender as a tie-breaker when proposals are equally ranked.
- The Extra criterion 1 rewards proposals that integrate gender dimensions in research.

²⁶ See Annex 7.7 for the evaluation chart that can help TNA Hosts select their candidates.

²⁷ Cf. the UN [Sustainable Development Goals](#) 10 (Reduced Inequality), 5 (Gender Equality), and 4 (Quality Education).

- We ensure gender-equitable evaluation, e.g., through a balanced composition of the evaluation committees and by training the reviewers in relation to unconscious bias.
- We monitor and report gender data on applicants and awardees.
- If the balance is not given, we promote inclusive outreach to encourage applications from underrepresented genders.

3.1.4 TNA Fellow Rights and Duties

Upon acceptance into the programme, TNA Fellows have the following rights and duties.

Rights:

1. They receive a grant to contribute to the costs of their research stay;
2. They will receive free access to the collections of the TNA Host Institution of their choice;
3. They will be able to access the TNA Host's expertise – if possible via a meeting with an onsite expert;
4. They can present their research at the TNA Host Institution of their choice if this is feasible;
5. They will receive (if desired) a TNA certificate of their stay;²⁸
6. RESILIENCE Membership (length and benefits to be determined), access to services and training.

Duties:

1. Communicate with the host institution(s) regarding my stay and access needs, e.g., specific collections/material, guidance from archival staff, access to research expertise;
2. Comply with rules and regulations of the host institution(s) and conform with the law of the host country in which the host institution(s) are located;
3. Arrange my own insurance to cover healthcare, travel and liability insurance with adequate cover for the whole duration of the Fellowship;
4. where feasible, present their research at the host institution (unless this proves unpractical or difficult, e.g., because the fellowship is too short or takes place during the summer months)
5. At minimum provide RESILIENCE with an abstract of their research and/or project, and where feasible provide dissemination materials about their Fellowship (blogs, articles, pictures, testimonies, etc.);
6. Complete the TNA report and evaluation no later than 6 weeks after the end of their fellowship;

²⁸ See Annex 7.10 for the current TNA Certificate Template.

7. Complete the TNA evaluation form 12 months after the end of their fellowship²⁹;
8. Inform RESILIENCE and the host institution of research outputs from the Fellowship once published (including but not limited to: academic articles, conference presentations, datasets, databases, scientific communication). The following statement should be used: "Research for this project was made possible through the support of the RESILIENCE TNA Fellowship Programme taken at [name of host institution]."

3.1.5 TNA Fellow Quality Monitoring: Procedures and Responsibilities

Quality monitoring for TNA Fellows is conducted in a number of different ways.

1. **Evaluating the TNA visits.** This will be done in two ways: (1) Evaluation form and annual report of the results (cf. Annex 7.9 for the current version of the evaluation); (2) Regular visits at TNA Hosts during a TNA visit by the national node coordinator.
2. **Terms and Conditions:** TNA Fellows are subject to the programme Terms and Conditions.³⁰
3. **Impact measurement and analysis.**³¹

3.2 Management of RESILIENCE TNA Hosts

Management of the TNA Hosts can be divided into two main categories: maintaining the TNA Hosting Network (all the duties surrounding hosting TNA Fellows) and growing the TNA Hosting Network. It is important to note that institutes will not need to be part of a national RESILIENCE consortium to become a TNA Host. As TNA Hosts, institutes join the national hosting network, whose point of contact will be the TNA national node coordinator. For the most up to date list of qualifying countries, we follow Horizon Europe Recommendations during the PP.

At the start of the PP onboarding new TNA Hosts was an active process where RESILIENCE pursued negotiations with potential new hosts. A passive process was set up as well, where interested institutions could contact RESILIENCE for more information. This passive process was adopted within the first year of the PP and maintained for its duration. During the implementation phase, interested institutes can apply to join via the same procedure.

²⁹ See RESILIENCE_WP5_D5.1_Impact Analysis (forthcoming December 2025).

³⁰ See https://docs.google.com/document/d/1RLqfYXdmwYA-Mh_yormFxpzWJNBeV5fvd79rSRMTf4s/edit?tab=t.o for the current version.

³¹ The RESILIENCE TNA Impact Assessment methodology is currently being developed in cooperation with WP5 and will be presented by WP5 in: RESILIENCE_WP5_D5.1_Impact Analysis (forthcoming December 2025).

3.2.1 Criteria of Excellence

The following formal criteria were developed for all TNA Host interested in joining the TNA Hosting Network. The aim of these criteria is to ensure the excellence, quality, and hospitality of the potential TNA Host via a transparent process.

1. Aware of the full commitment required to fulfil minimum duties of a TNA host **(yes/no)**.
2. Dean/Director of the institution has signed the memorandum of understanding **(yes/no)**.
3. Has appointed a TNA Coordinator and TNA Contact Person (can be one person) **(yes/no)**.
4. Holds one or more academic collections relevant to the study of religion **(yes/no)**.
5. Host institution has a number of in-house experts/senior scholars affiliated with disciplines related to the study of religion and/or experts on the collections in their holdings **(yes/no)**.
6. Host institution is located within Horizon Europe list of European nations³² **(yes/no)**.
7. Host institution is GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) compliant and inasmuch as possible operates according to OA and FAIR principles **(yes/no)**.
8. Host institution has an online presence (newsletters, social media, website) which can be utilized for RESILIENCE communication and PR **(yes/no)**.
9. Host institution intends to provide a safe space to excellent researchers regardless of gender, age, religion, nationality or impairments **(yes/no)**.

These criteria can largely be maintained for the next phase of the TNA Programme, with this exception that the next phase will likely require some legal and financial criteria to be included as well.

3.2.2 Rights and Duties

Each TNA Host signs a grant agreement with RESILIENCE outlining the duties and responsibilities of each partner. In the preparatory phase the rights and duties of both the TNA Host and RESILIENCE TNA were outlined in a Memorandum of Understanding. That version was temporary, and did not include any financial or legal obligations. For the funded version of the programme, we have developed a new MoU that takes the future legal, financial, and administrative structure into account together with EHRI-ERIC, with whom we have collaborated to align the formal procedures for the programme where possible. See Annex 7.1 for this final of the MoU.

³² For the most up to date list of qualifying countries, please see: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/news/all-research-and-innovation-news/updates-association-third-countries-horizon-europe-2021-12-21_en

The TNA Host commits to:

1. Notifying RESILIENCE of the maximum number of TNA Fellows they can host as well as the maximum number of weeks per year during which they can host Fellows.
2. Appoint a RESILIENCE TNA coordinator responsible for coordinating and ensuring the effective implementation of the above activities and informing RESILIENCE of that person's name and contact details.
3. Hosting the Fellows and providing physical access, as required, including free access to relevant collections and/or expertise, as well as a free desk space with internet access.
4. Communicating with the Fellows before and during the fellowship period, including arrangements related to the timing and practicalities of stay.
5. Facilitating the Fellows' introduction to the Host Institution, such as providing an orientation tour of relevant facilities (e.g., library and archive), introducing key staff and experts relevant to the Fellows' research and where possible including a meeting with an onsite expert (e.g. archival support, research guidance, collection expert).
6. Where possible, including the Fellows in relevant institutional activities taking place during their stay (e.g., events, research meetings, discussions, workshops, conferences) and offering the Fellows the opportunity to present their research.
7. Report to RESILIENCE on the performance of the TNA program and help to develop and improve the TNA program and its procedures.
8. Participate in promoting RESILIENCE TNA, TNA Scholars, and TNA research results, through internal and external communication channels.
9. Permit RESILIENCE to publish a description of your physical and digital collections on your TNA Host webpage as a part of the RESILIENCE website.

RESILIENCE commits to:

1. Managing the financial and administrative aspect of ring-fenced funds allocated to cover a set number of access weeks per year, as determined annually.
2. Allocating dedicated staff time for the financial and administrative management of Fellowships, including the management of the TNA Portal and the TNA Calls for Proposals, the coordination of the RESILIENCE TNA Programme Hosting Network, and the organisation of the peer review process.
3. Offering access to RESILIENCE Marketplace.
4. Carrying out communication and outreach activities at the EU level.
5. Maintaining and developing a network of Fellowship alumni.
6. Coordinating, monitoring and evaluating of Fellowship scheme.

3.2.3 TNA Host Application Workflow

During the PP a detailed application workflow was developed which has proven itself over the past two years. While still requiring some fine-tuning, especially if the TNA Hosting Network scales up exponentially, experience has shown that the emphasis on personal contact demonstrated below is crucial for the success of subsequent TNA Fellow visits. With the exception of step 1, TNA Host applications will not be conducted via the TNA Portal, since they require the formal agreement of RESILIENCE.

Step 1: An institute contacts RESILIENCE TNA via the TNA Portal, providing basic details and motivation.

Step 2: The TNA Management Team conducts a short investigation and decides whether to proceed. If yes, they create an account for the prospective host, which will include the following information and documentation:

1. Template of the TNA Host Memorandum of Understanding.³³
2. Criteria of Excellence (see above).
3. A short questionnaire to gain insight into the exact expertise and collections on offer.³⁴
4. Link to the other TNA Host webpages from the TNA Portal.

Should the TNA Portal not be implemented yet, these documents will be sent via email. Once the TNA Host fills in the questionnaire online, the TNA Management Team sets up a meeting with the new host to discuss key rights and duties, outline the grant management process, discuss the available collections and archives, and ensures that the TNA Host fully understands everything that is required. A number of guides and tips were collected in the PP phase to aid this part of the process, which will be collected into a single guide for the next phase.³⁵ The following commitments should be clarified:

1. Admissions Criteria, MoU, and rights/duties of a TNA Host,
2. Appointing a TNA Coordinator,
3. Providing a workspace, access to collections, and all the requested materials,
4. Commitment towards introducing TNA scholars to onsite expert(s),
5. Timeline of the Call for Applications: application process, deadlines, call for TNA Scholars.
6. Introduction to the TNA Portal.

It is especially important to highlight the appointment criteria for the TNA Host Coordinator and the legal requirements and time frame needed to sign the agreement. Experience has shown that given that this often requires a high-level faculty or institute member, the process can take some time. To conclude this step, the TNA Programme Coordinator writes a short recommendation report for the Peer Review Board.³⁶

³³ See Annex 7.1 for the template currently in use.

³⁴ [See here for the extensive version](#). This has been used for the first two years of the PP, but was deemed too long and unwieldy in practice. An updated version is still in development.

³⁵ See <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1BCNbAM86gIxcDgYqymirFv3XmoAxcgWaP> for the current guide, email templates, meeting checklists, and more.

³⁶ See Annex 7.2 for the current template of this TNA Host Recommendation Report.

Step 3: The TNA Peer Review Board meets every six months to discuss the TNA Host applications received.³⁷ This can also be done a-synchronously via email. These applications are summarized and prepared by the TNA Programme Coordinator. Each board member makes an individual decision according to the information included in the report. This decision is added to the report by the TNA Programme Coordinator, who communicates it to the respective candidate TNA Hosts. Board members are obliged to vote: three votes suffices for a positive advice. In case the board cannot come to a decision, the application is forward to the RESILIENCE Executive Director, who has the final vote. Each TNA Host is then confirmed by the GenA.

Step 4: The TNA Host is informed of the results. They will in turn inform TNA Management within a certain time frame whether they wish to accept and move forward with the process or not. Once both parties have agreed, the agreement is made up and signed. All the agreements are collected before every meeting of the RESILIENCE General Assembly, who finally confirms the acceptance of the new TNA Host(s).

3.2.4 TNA Host Onboarding Workflow

The first step for onboarding a new TNA Host is the appointment of the TNA Coordinator and/or TNA Contact Person. They will also form the point of contact for RESILIENCE TNA, and are responsible for delivering and checking the information needed to create a TNA Host profile in the TNA Portal. This information can already be gathered before the GenA greenlights the decision, but cannot be published. Once the profile is completed to the satisfaction of both parties, it will be published, at which point the TNA Host can begin to participate in the programme.

Currently each TNA Host has their own webpage on the [RESILIENCE TNA website](#), showcasing their key resources and expertise. This includes both physical and virtual resources. In general, virtual sources and services available onsite at the TNA Host. In some cases, once a fellow has been accepted TNA Hosts can add to this benefit in the shape of access to digital collections and services. The TNA Portal will take over this role in the future version of the programme.

3.2.5 TNA Visit Workflow

One month after the application deadline, the TNA hosts and the TNA Evaluation Board have decided which applicants are accepted and which are rejected, and the TNA Programme Coordinator informs the applicants. If the TNA Portal is implemented all of this will take place automatically via the Portal. Then the local TNA contact person begins to make the arrangements for the research stay with the TNA fellow. The figure below outlines the process without the inclusion of the portal.

³⁷ This length of time is subject further insight, as currently it is not clear how often TNA Host applications will be received in the next RESILIENCE Phase.

1. First Contact	TNA Fellow	Ask for dates, resources, experts; clarify conditions	TNA Host Contact		
2. ASAP	TNA Fellow	Agree on dates, resources, experts, conditions	TNA Host Contact	Ensure resources are available at agreed dates	TNA Host (Library/Collection/University/Facility)
3. At least 2 weeks before TNA stay			TNA Host Contact	Arrange library card/ access passes	TNA Host (Library/Collection/University/Facility)
	TNA Fellow	Inform about arrangements, clarify organisational matters	TNA Host Contact	Arrange meeting(s), participation in acad. activities	Local Expert(s)/ Research Group(s)
4. At least 1 week before TNA stay			TNA Host Contact	Prepare research needs: resources, office, etc.	TNA Host (Library/Collection/University/Facility)
5. During the TNA stay	TNA Fellow	Arrange Meet and Greet; contact / support	TNA Host Contact	Scientific support	Local Expert(s)/ Research Group(s)
6. One week after TNA stay	TNA Fellow	Request for Evaluation	TNA Portal		
7. ASAP			TNA Programme Coordinator	Feedback and discussion on results of evaluation	TNA Host Contact and Coordinator

Figure 2: TNA Stay Workflow

3.2.6 Quality Monitoring: Procedures and Responsibilities

Quality monitoring for TNA Hosts is conducted in a number of different ways.

1. **Biannual TNA Host Trainings.** These were created and trialled in the PP phase for new hosts to create a uniform sense of experience and quality. They outline the workflow, key responsibilities, and include testimonies and experiences from TNA Fellows. Currently these are still confidential.
2. **Evaluation form and annual report.** Each TNA Host will be asked to fill in an evaluation form annually.³⁸ The TNA Management Team compiles and analyses the results, and reports on the status quo, as well as possible recommendations.
3. **Impact measurement and analysis.**³⁹ This will be fully conducted by RESILIENCE Headquarters. The procedures for this will be developed during the next phase of RESILIENCE.⁴⁰

4 Long-Term Strategies of the TNA Programme

The previous chapters described the key aspects of running and maintaining the TNA Programme during the RESILIENCE implementation phase. This chapter outlines the long-term plans that have been developed as a result of the PP phase, which should be taken into account for the next phase of the programme.

4.1 TNA Portal

Multiple references have been made to the TNA Portal. The ultimate aim of the TNA programme is to provide fast, efficient access to collections and experts via an ongoing call, where RESILIENCE functions as a facilitator rather than organizer. The need for an online platform became clear during the first two years of the PP. In that phase, TNA Calls for Proposals were run on an occasional basis: two annual calls, and four bi-annual calls. The switch towards the latter took place in 2024, halfway the prototyping phase, to shift the calls away from the summer period, allowing scholars to apply for summer research stays – a period which was not possible to apply for with the timing of the previous two calls. However, two calls per year is still not a very flexible nor efficient format. For the future version of the TNA Programme, we would like to move towards a more regular application cycle where possible, facilitated by a RESILIENCE TNA Online Portal.

The first two years of the preparatory phase were dedicated to setting up the prototype TNA Programme, and to create and grow the initial TNA Hosting Network. That work revealed the need for a dedicated TNA Portal. However, no effort or resources were foreseen at this stage of the project for prototyping or developing such a portal.

³⁸ This was launched in August 2024 for the first time. See <https://www.resilience-ri.eu/evaluation-form-tna-host/> for the questionnaire.

³⁹ The RESILIENCE TNA Impact Assessment methodology is currently being developed in cooperation with WP5 and will be presented by WP5 in: RESILIENCE_WP5_D5.1_ Impact Analysis (forthcoming December 2025).

⁴⁰ See also the D5.1 Impact Analysis.

From 2023-2025, ITSERR, the Italian national project in support of RESILIENCE, was able to develop a prototype TNA Portal that has currently entered the testing phase. ITSERR will conclude in April 2026, after which the prototype will be hosted and maintained for a maximum of five years by the project partners. Should RESILIENCE be successful in its Transition to Implementation Phase (TIP) application (2026-2028) we will further develop the portal, with the aim of launching it by 2028. If not, further development will commence in 2030, which is when the Financial Sustainability Plan foresees the inclusion of a fulltime software developer within RESILIENCE.

The TNA Portal has three specific goals that answer the challenges highlighted in the case studies above:

1. To automate the effort required to run the TNA Programme as much possible. This includes the TNA Call for Proposals, the TNA Fellow applications, the TNA Peer Review Process, the TNA Fellow and TNA Host evaluations, and a searchable overview of the TNA Host Institutions. In this way we can reserve partner effort for 1) evaluating and improving processes, 2) implementing new initiatives and 3) networking and collaboration.
2. To make the TNA network more efficient and more easily accessible for TNA Fellows. The portal will allow users to search for RESILIENCE TNA institutes and their specific physical and virtual collections, as well as researchers according to academic discipline, experts, and research topic. It will do this by importing data via a RSS feed from the institution, sourced from publicly available profiles and information.
3. To create a networking and collaboration platform for TNA Hosts: GLAM institutes, archives and libraries, institutes of higher education. In the long run, such a platform can provide an ongoing, sustainable environment which can serve as the starting point for transnational collaboration on the institutional level, with the aim of increasing the success rate of large grant applications, forming a negotiating block for projects involving the for-profit sector, as well as knowledge and staff exchanges.

The version of the portal includes the following key features:

1. **Key User Roles:** TNA Manager – HQ / EU level, TNA National Host Coordinator, Peer Reviewer and TNA Fellow.
1. **TNA Application Dashboard.** This section automatizes the application process for TNA Fellows where possible. Applications are automatically forwarded to the relevant TNA Host, RESILIENCE Communications officer, and RESILIENCE TNA programme officer. The TNA Coordinator of the Host will then respond with the results of the application. If positive, they will then take the first steps for planning the TNA visit. The TNA Coordinator communicates the results to the RESILIENCE Programme Officer. Evaluation forms will then be sent by the system, based on the dates of the application. ORCID IDs form part of the application.
2. **TNA Manager Dashboard.** Intended for the TNA officer at RESILIENCE HQ, this dashboard allows the manager to write, edit, and publish TNA Calls, manage the peer review process, manage TNA Fellow applications, and onboard new TNA Hosts.

3. **List of searchable TNA Hosts.** These are searchable by institute name, city and country, type of institute (HEI - University, Library, Archive, Museum, other), and available expertise.
4. **TNA Programme Evaluations.** Evaluation links will be sent to the TNA Fellow after their research stay via the TNA Portal. These will be summarized and analysed by the Portal into a short report. That report will be supplemented and finalized by the RESILIENCE Programme Officer, and sent to RESILIENCE HQ. The evaluations for the TNA Hosts will be conducted annually, and fully analysed and reported on by the programme officer to RESILIENCE HQ.

The TNA Portal is currently still in its prototyping phase. The screenshots below give some insights into the design and workflows, but are still a work-in-progress and should not be viewed as the definitive product. The ITSERR project will run until April 2026, after which that version will at minimum be maintained and stored for a maximum of five years. All the information in the screenshots are examples and do not represent the actual content of the TNA Programme.

Figure 3: Call for Proposals

Figure 4: TNA Manager Dashboard: Managing TNA Fellow Proposals

Figure 5: TNA Manager Dashboard: Managing TNA Calls

The screenshot shows the ITSEERR TNA Manager interface. On the left is a sidebar with navigation options: Dashboard, Hosts, Peoples, Manage Calls, Proposals, Expenses, Visits, and Resources. The main content area is titled 'Host' and displays a table of TNA Hosts. The table has columns for TITLE, DESCRIPTION, and WEBSITE. There are 6 hosts listed, each with a blue pencil icon for editing and a red trash icon for deletion. A '+ Host' button is located in the top right of the table area.

TITLE	DESCRIPTION	WEBSITE
Institute of Information Science and Technologies (ISTI - CNR) "Alessandro Faedo" - Pisa		https://www.itseerr.it/institute-of-information-science-and-technologies-isti-cnr-alessandro-faedo-pisa/
RD-Faculty of Theology and Religion, University of Oxford	Oxford's Faculty "has been at the very heart of religious debate, reform, and turmoil in the British Isles for eight centuries," and "embrac[es] wholeheartedly the challenges of the twenty-first..."	https://www.theology.ox.ac.uk
RD-Faculty of Theology and Religious Studies, KU Leuven	Founded in 1432, the Faculty "focuses on training students and researchers" where "theology and religious studies mutually enrich one another", programmes are taught in Dutch and English and "are..."	https://theo.kuleuven.be/en?utm_source=chatgpt.com
RD-School of Divinity (New College), University of Edinburgh	Located in the city centre at New College, the School offers "an inspiring setting to study" Theology and Religious Studies with "a real sense of community," including its own library, café and...	https://divinity.ed.ac.uk
RD-Faculty of Theology, University of Oslo	The Faculty conducts research and teaching in Theology, Christian Studies, Inter-religious Studies and Diaconal Studies.	https://www.tf.uio.no/english
RD-Faculty of Theology, University of Copenhagen	The Faculty's main activity is research, education and dissemination in theology and African Studies, engaging actively in internationalisation and collaboration with employers of its graduates.	https://teol.ku.dk/english

Figure 6: TNA Manager Dashboard: Managing TNA Hosts

Figure 7: Frontend: Example of a TNA Host Page

4.2 Expanding the TNA Hosting Network

Expansion of the TNA Hosting Network will be an ongoing and carefully curated part of the TNA Programme. The priorities listed below should be kept in mind for the first two years of the programme, after which evaluation and monitoring of the project should dictate future strategies. Throughout however, the network should remain as diverse as possible on the geographic, religious and disciplinary level.

4.2.1 GLAM Sector

For galleries and museums, the procedures and workflows remain largely similar to those of research institutes. The key difference is that unlike institutes of higher education, not many museums or art galleries will have experience hosting visiting research fellows, though this very much depends on the institute itself. Talks with potential GLAM hosts will therefore have to be more extensive to ensure that the TNA experience remains of the same level of excellence. Experiences during the PP with the Comenius Museum in the Czech Republic were very positive however, and has shown that the potential for including this sector is

worthwhile: within the study of religion there is a strong movement towards material history, oral history, and even audiovisual history. RESILIENCE would be offering an entirely unique service by including exchanges with museums and galleries in its offer of TNA Hosts. Many of our TNA Hosts will have existing connections and collaborations with national museums which can be leveraged to this end, though here too the expansion will have to be curated carefully to guarantee excellence. During the next RESILIENCE phase the collaboration with E-RIHS will also be instigated, which will include an investigation into a possible collaboration for the TNA Programme for heritage studies.

In addition to museums and archives we will also explore the potential of including religious institutes such as monasteries, churches, mosques, and synagogues. A good current example is the Bektashi Headquarters, who are one of the first TNA hosts within this category. However, here it is clear that specific criteria and guidelines need to be developed, as well as relationships cultivated that can mediate between the researcher and the religious institute. This will require careful negotiation and monitoring on the part of RESILIENCE, while at the same time providing access to an entirely unique resource within the study of religion and the humanities.

4.2.2 Geographic Expansion

In line with the communication strategy, the initial focus within Europe will be Eastern Europe and the Balkans. Plans were in place for MENA expansion, but given the current regional instability this has been put on hold for now. Expansion towards Ireland/the UK, Scandinavia, Spain, and Central Europe is crucial to maintain European diversity and the sustainability of the programme, and discussions with partner institutes in these member states are still ongoing.

4.2.3 Creating an Active Network

In addition to these concrete expansion strategies, the other emphasis will be on expanding outgoing as well as incoming mobility. The first two calls were chiefly focused on external TNA Fellows applying to visit a TNA Host, with the TNA Host functioning as a passive recipient of applications. With the implementation of the TNA Portal we foresee that this will more of a two-way street, in which TNA Hosts actively present the programme to their scholars as an exchange option. The goal is to achieve an energetic network of incoming and outgoing exchanges for each host. To that end, in the next RESILIENCE phase, an Alumni Network for TNA Fellows will be created using the database of TNA Fellows that was put together during the PP phase.

4.3 Risks and Mitigations

A number of risks have already been identified at this stage of the project; we also foresee a number of challenges for the upcoming transition phase. The list below is not exhaustive, but gives a good indication of the main point.

4.3.1 Risks concerning the transition to the RESILIENCE Implementation Phase.

- Unfunded TNA during implementation phase.
- Delays in the development of the TNA Portal.
- Delays in the transition from PP to Implementation phase.

In all these cases the in-kind version of the TNA Programme can be continued for a longer period of time to facilitate the transition. Individual TNA Hosts can be contacted for local funding possibilities, which can be included in the TNA benefits for that TNA host. Delays in the development of the portal are easier to mitigate, as the current RESILIENCE TNA website is sufficiently developed to run the current version of the programme.

4.3.2 Risks concerning the TNA Hosting Network

- Challenging to maintain a brand of excellence across such a wide variety (geographical, thematic, size) of institutions, thereby risking a too broad/vague brand of TNA.
 - Mitigation: Develop targeted strategies to recruit suitable hosts and prioritize institutes that will join RESILIENCE.
- Theological and religious studies archives, libraries, and institutions are often quite small and might struggle with fulfilling the minimal duties, both on an institutional level, and on a staff level.
 - Mitigation: We foresee that this will be less of an issue during the implementation phase than during the PP phase, since the distributed structure of RESILIENCE and the embedding of the TNA Programme into the national nodes will help to shorten communication lines between TNA Hosts and the national TNA Coordinator, thereby allowing for more support on a case-by-case basis.
- While smaller institutions counterbalance the lack of dedicated funds with the visibility gained by being part of RESILIENCE, bigger institutions, which are already well known, ask for unique benefits in comparison to other programmes and/or their everyday activities.
 - The benefits for larger institutions relate more to access to the RI as a whole, and will become less of a challenge as RESILIENCE transitions towards an ERIC.

4.3.3 Risks concerning the Individual TNA Stays

- The expertise requested by the TNA user is not available in facility/library.
 - This is something that the TNA Host Coordinator should flag upon receiving the application. In that case the TNA applicant will be informed of this and if possible recommended to a different TNA Host that does possess the required expertise. In the case of experts, this is

something we ask TNA Hosts to fulfil if possible, but to mitigate via an online meeting or via alternative meetings if the requested expert is not available.

- Lack of TNA proposals from qualified applicants.
 - Should this remain consistent the National Node Coordinator will plan a meeting to determine a strategy for mitigating this, e.g. more communication and PR in their specific expertise.
- The planned TNA budget is not sufficient for the TNA user due to unforeseen price increases.
 - This will have to be mitigated via shorter research stays and/or more digital and virtual research stays. If there is an option to increase the budget that is the preferred solution.
- A host institution withdraws from the RESILIENCE TNA programme to which TNA fellows are still to join.
 - While this is obviously not encouraged, it has happened once during the PP phase, for reasons outside of the TNA Host's control. The immediate solution is to try to arrange for these fellows to stay at the institution for the remaining time and/or to find an alternative host institution.
- A pandemic/disaster/war and other events prevent physical access.
 - In this case we will explore the options of virtual and digital access, and focus on finding alternative hosts not located in the affected region.

5 Communication and Impact

This section will address communication strategies and how the impact of the TNA Programme will be measured from the implementation phase onward. Both of these have been, or will be developed in close collaboration with Communication and Impact Work Units, such as the current WP₄ (Communication and Dissemination) and WP₅ (Impact).

5.1 Communication Strategy Frame for TNA

It is recommended that the "Communication Strategy Frame for the RESILIENCE TNA Programme", which was developed in the PP by WP₄ in cooperation with WP₂, be continuously followed up for an agile development of the communication strategy.⁴¹ The strategy aims to reach the target groups relevant to RESILIENCE, including potential TNA fellows, potential TNA hosts and the flow of information to other

⁴¹ Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan, chap. 3.3, see [RESILIENCE WP₄ CDEP](#) (D4.2, November 2024). Communication Strategy Frame for TNA: see Annex 7.11.

target groups. The framework for the implementation phase must be adapted to the changed conditions (funding opportunities, modified scope, etc.).

5.2 Guide for the TNA Communication Workflow

To ensure the communication and dissemination of each RESILIENCE TNA scholarship, the WP4 CDE developed a TNA Communication Workflow guide, which describes the specific measures to be taken. This guide can be used as a basis for the communication workflow in the next phase. Results are news items on the RESILIENCE website and/or on the RESILIENCE social media channels.

5.3 Action Plan for Social Media Content

A social media strategy should be included in the TNA communication strategy framework. It is recommended to operate with an Action Plan that acts as a calendar for all social media content and ensures that all relevant planned actions are shared on social media. In the context of TNA, this includes news about the TNA research stays, the calls, news about TNA hosts, webinars for TNA fellows or hosts, results of these various activities, publications due to RESILIENCE TNA and other topics of interest in this regard.⁴²

5.4 Measuring Impact

The RESILIENCE work package on impact is still in the process of developing a strategy and management plan for measuring impact of the future RI. As one of the few active services, they prioritized the creation of an impact plan for TNA. This section summarizes the key aspects of this plan, though it should be noted that this is still a work in progress.

Within TNA, they have identified three levels of data that need to be taken into account: output data, outcome data, and impact data. Output data consists of measurable results. For TNA this includes the number of TNA Hosts and Fellows and their demographics (institutional affiliation, geographic location, level of education), as well as the diversity of participants and their evaluation of TNA activities. Outcome data provides insight on the benefits experienced by Fellows as well as Hosts in the TNA programme, such as acquired knowledge and skills, scientific publications, international research collaborations, and increase in access of collections. Finally, impact data captures the long-term effects of the programme, providing insights on changes in the organizational capacity and societal resilience. This also includes the impact on underrepresented groups and regions, economic impact via innovation, and solutions to global challenges. The work package on impact is working out indicators and approaches for measuring this within the context of the RI as a whole, as well as the role of TNA within it.

⁴² Cf. as an example D4.2, Attachment 2: Action Plan M13-M27 (not part of the public deliverable), in: [RESILIENCE WP4 CDEP](#) (D4.2, November 2024).

5.5 Open Science & FAIR Principle

In line with the RESILIENCE Service Strategy, TNA intends to “[...] safeguard our community’s research output should be both FAIR and sustainable”. In the case of TNA, we incorporate FAIR as a guiding principle in its service management, and focus on Open Science and Open Access as guiding principles within the context of the TNA Programme.⁴³ The most concrete example for the current stage of the programme of this is that we ask that all scientific output that relates to the TNA Visit of a TNA Fellow be published Open Access, *where this is feasible*. Due to the individual or institutional costs associated with open access publication this is not something we wish to enforce, but we will encourage it where possible.

5.6 Data Management Policy

This will be developed during the next phase RESILIENCE in line with the further development of the TNA Platform, as the data will be gathered and stored via this platform. All personal data acquired during the PP will be deleted by the end of this phase.

6 Next Steps

The RESILIENCE TNA Programme forms a crucial part of the current and future RESILIENCE ecosystem. It ensures physical access to sources and collections, and helps increase the networking currency of both individual TNA Fellows and the TNA Hosting Network. The relatively high number of TNA Fellows during the preparatory phase shows that there is a need for such a service, especially for early and mid-career scholars. Funding the programme will help facilitate access for those scholars who are currently not able to fund their own research stay, as well as contribute to increasing equality of access across Europe.

In the next phase, which is estimated to last from June 2026 till June 2028, RESILIENCE will transition towards its implementation phase. During this phase, the TNA Programme will undergo the final testing and updates necessary for implementation in 2028, namely:

1. The TNA Portal will be further tested and, should the funding be granted, finalized and ready for implementation.
2. The collaboration with EHRI-EU will be formalized, and our respective TNA Programmes will be integrated where necessary and possible.
3. The collaboration with other RIs, notably E-RIHS, will be sought, with the aim of producing a common TNA Programme accessed through a common TNA Portal.

⁴³ [RESILIENCE WP2 D2.1 Services Preparation and Implementation Strategy](#), p. 9.

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7.1 TNA Host Memorandum of Understanding

RESILIENCE TNA Fellowship Programme Memorandum of Understanding

Between

The European Research Infrastructure on Religious Studies (hereafter RESILIENCE), a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) established by the European Commission Implementing Decision (EU) [INSERT DATE], having its headquarter in Palermo, Italy (“RESILIENCE”)

and

[Insert name], a [type of organisation] whose registered office is at [insert address], (“Host Institution”)

Hereinafter collectively referred to as the “Parties” and individually as “Party”.

Background

The RESILIENCE Transnational Access Programme (“RESILIENCE TNA Programme”) is a short-term research fellowship for individual researchers (“Fellows”). It offers physical and virtual access to an expanding network of European institutions and libraries, with the aim of facilitating and fostering easy access to sources, resources, expertise and services for researchers in the study of religion in all their synchronic and diachronic variety, as well as promoting and disseminating collections, institutions, and archives. By participating in the RESILIENCE TNA Programme, institutions benefit from increased recognition and dissemination of their collections, can access a top-level network of researchers and institutions related to the study of religion, and participate in an international exchange network of researchers, scholars, archivists, librarians, stakeholders, and policy makers.

Considering the desire of the [insert name] to become a RESILIENCE TNA host, this Memorandum of Understanding (“MoU”) lists the mutual roles and responsibilities of RESILIENCE-ERIC and the Host Institution, as well as the terms and conditions governing their collaboration within the framework of the RESILIENCE TNA Fellowship Programme.

Fellowship

RESILIENCE will award fellowships to individual Fellows selected in accordance with its internal procedures. Each fellowship shall typically last between one (1) and six (6) week(s) and cover a country-specific subsistence allowance and reasonable travel costs, both paid directly by RESILIENCE in accordance with its internal policy.

Rights and obligations of the Parties:

RESILIENCE shall be responsible for:

1. The financial and administrative management of ring-fenced funds allocated to cover a set number of access weeks per year, as determined annually.
2. Allocating dedicated staff time for the financial and administrative management of Fellowships, including the management of the TNA Portal and the TNA Calls for Proposals, the coordination of the RESILIENCE TNA Programme Hosting Network, and the organisation of the peer review process.
3. Offering access to RESILIENCE Marketplace.
4. Carrying out communication and outreach activities at the EU level.
5. Maintaining and developing a network of Fellowship alumni.
6. Coordinating, monitoring and evaluating of Fellowship scheme.

The Host institutions shall be responsible for:

1. Notifying RESILIENCE of the maximum number of TNA Fellows they can host as well as the maximum number of weeks per year during which they can host Fellows.
2. Appoint a RESILIENCE TNA coordinator responsible for coordinating and ensuring the effective implementation of the above activities and informing RESILIENCE of that person's name and contact details.
3. Hosting the Fellows and providing physical access, as required, including free access to relevant collections and/or expertise, as well as a free desk space with internet access.
4. Communicating with the Fellows before and during the fellowship period, including arrangements related to the timing and practicalities of stay.
5. Facilitating the Fellows' introduction to the Host Institution, such as providing an orientation tour of relevant facilities (e.g., library and archive), introducing key staff and experts relevant to the Fellows' research and where possible including a meeting with an onsite expert (e.g. archival support, research guidance, collection expert).
6. Where possible, including the Fellows in relevant institutional activities taking place during their stay (e.g., events, research meetings, discussions, workshops, conferences) and offering the Fellows the opportunity to present their research.
7. Report to RESILIENCE on the performance of the TNA program and help to develop and improve the TNA program and its procedures.

8. Participate in promoting RESILIENCE TNA, TNA Scholars, and TNA research results, through internal and external communication channels.
9. Permit RESILIENCE to publish a description of physical and digital collections available at the Host Institution on a dedicated TNA Host webpage as a part of the RESILIENCE website.

Financial arrangements

The Host Institution acknowledges that the Fellowship funding is provided directly to the Fellows and that RESILIENCE shall not provide funds to the Hosting Institution under this MoU.

The costs related to the central financial and administrative management of the RESILIENCE TNA Programme, including the fellowship awards, shall be borne by RESILIENCE.

The Host Institution shall not be responsible for financial or administrative aspects of the Fellowship grant itself, but other costs incurred by the Host Institution in connection with its participation in the RESILIENCE TNA Programme shall be borne by the Host Institution and shall be considered as in-kind contribution to RESILIENCE.

Each Party shall bear its own costs in connection with the implementation of this MoU, unless otherwise agreed in writing.

Liability and insurance

[The next paragraph should be adapted on a case-by-case basis]

Each Party shall be solely responsible for its acts and omissions under this MoU.

RESILIENCE shall ensure that Fellows are informed of their responsibility to obtain appropriate insurance coverage for the duration of the Fellowship, including health, accident, and third-party liability insurance.

The Host Institution shall not be liable for any personal injury, loss, or damage suffered by the Fellow, unless caused by its gross negligence or wilful misconduct. The Host Institution shall maintain third-party liability insurance, which may cover the Fellow as a visitor.

Confidentiality and data protection

The Parties shall ensure that any personal data exchanged in the context of this MoU is processed in accordance with applicable data protection laws.

Confidential information shared between the Parties shall be treated as such and not disclosed to third parties without prior written consent, unless required by law.

Duration and termination

This MoU shall become effective on the date of the last signature and shall remain in effect for five (5) years from that date. It shall automatically renew for successive periods of five (5) years unless either Party gives at least three (3) months written notice before the end of the term. This MoU may be terminated prior to expiry in the following circumstances:

- a) by either Party for convenience, upon providing at least three (3) months' prior notice to the other Party;
- b) at any time, by mutual written agreement of the Parties, or,
- c) by a non-breaching Party, in the event of a material breach by the other Party, which is not remedied within ten (10) days of receipt of written notice specifying the breach.

Termination of this MoU shall not affect any rights of obligations accrued prior to the date of termination.

Amendments

This MoU may only be amended or modified by a written agreement signed by duly authorised representatives of both Parties.

Assignment

Neither Party may assign this MoU without the prior written consent of the other. Nothing in this MoU constitutes a partnership, joint venture or agency relationship between the Parties.

Dispute resolution

The Parties shall seek to resolve any dispute arising under this MoU amicably and in good faith through their designated representatives.

Date and signature host institution

Date and signature RESILIENCE

7.2 TNA Host Recommendation Report

General Information

RESILIENCE Contact Person: [Full Name, Institutional affiliation]

Name TNA Host Institution: [Full name and acronym]

Date of Application: [dd/mm/yy]

Weblink institute:

Type of institute: [Archive/Library/Institute of Higher Education/Art Gallery/Museum/other]

Nationality:

Main language(s) spoken at institute:

Admissions Criteria TNA Hosts

Please indicate "yes" or "no" for each criterium:

1. Aware of the financial commitment required to fulfill minimum duties of a TNA host. **(yes/no)**
2. Dean/Director of the institution has signed (or is willing to sign) the memorandum of understanding **(yes/no)**
3. Has appointed a TNA Coordinator and TNA Contact Person (can be one person) **(yes/no)**
4. Holds one or more academic collections relevant to the field of religious studies **(yes/no)**
5. Host institution has a number of in-house experts/senior scholars affiliated with disciplines related to religious studies and/or experts on the collections in their holdings **(yes/no)**
6. Host institution is located within Horizon Europe list of European nations **(yes/no)**
7. Host institution is GDPR compliant and operates according to OA and FAIR principles **(yes/no)**
8. Host institution has an online presence (newsletters, social media, website) which can be utilized for RESILIENCE communication and PR **(yes/no)**
9. Host institution aims to provide a safe space to excellent researchers regardless of gender, age, nationality or impairments **(yes/no)**

Minimum Duties TNA Host

The TNA Host has been informed of, and has indicated a commitment towards the minimum duties listed below required to host a TNA scholar:

1. Agree to a minimum number of TNA recipients per academic year. **(Yes/no. [number])**
2. Review and accept TNA applications for your institution, using the TNA Review Criteria. **(yes/no)**
3. Ensure the provision of a comfortable workspace for each TNA recipient. **(yes/no)**
4. Match TNA recipients with at minimum one onsite scholar/expert. **(yes/no)**
5. Report to RESILIENCE on the performance of the TNA program and help to develop and improve the TNA program and its procedures. **(yes/no)**
6. Participate in promoting RESILIENCE TNA, TNA Scholars, and TNA research results, through internal and external communication channels. **(yes/no)**
7. Permit RESILIENCE to publish a description of your physical and digital collections on your TNA Host webpage as a part of the RESILIENCE website. **(yes/no)**

Additional Services

The TNA Host has these additional services at their disposal, which they have indicated can be utilized by potential TNA Scholars:

1. [...]
2. [...]

Recommendation RESILIENCE Contact Person

Please indicate in a few lines your official recommendation to the TNA Host Evaluation Working Group, and explain why.

[...]

7.3 TNA Host Evaluation Form

The TNA Host Evaluation form was developed in 2024. It can be accessed online here:

[TNA Host Evaluation Form](#).

7.4 TNA Fellow Grant Agreement

The RESILIENCE Transnational Access Programme offers physical and virtual access to an expanding network of European institutions and libraries. Its aim is to facilitate and foster easy access to sources, resources, expertise and services for researchers in Religious Studies in all their synchronic and diachronic variety, as well as promoting and disseminating collections, institutions, and archives. This document lists the mutual roles and responsibilities of each party in taking part in the TNA Programme and is intended to promote and ensure the excellence of the RESILIENCE TNA Fellowship Programme.

This Confirmation of Fellowship Terms sets out the terms and conditions under which the undersigned individual (the "Fellow") accepts the award of a RESILIENCE TNA Fellowship ("RTF") granted by RESILIENCE under the TNA Fellowship Programme.

Personal Information

Full Name:

Date of Birth:

Home Address:

Email Address:

Phone Number:

Citizenship/Nationality:

IBAN:

SWIFT/BIC:

Name Account Holder:

Project Information

Title Fellowship Project:

Host Institution(s):

Length and Start Date of Fellowship:

Acceptance of Terms

By signing this Confirmation of Fellowship Terms, I confirm the following:

- I have been awarded the Fellowship to conduct research at the Host Institution(s) listed above, as approved by the RESILIENCE TNA Host Evaluation Board Committee following a competitive process.
- I understand that I will receive a flat-rate subsistence allowance for the duration of the fellowship, paid in Euros by RESILIENCE at the start of the fellowship, to contribute ONLY to accommodation, subsistence, and local travel costs. Should a TNA Host offer in-kind accommodation, this takes precedence.
- I will be reimbursed for reasonable travel costs up to a maximum amount in accordance with RESILIENCE policies and upon submission of valid supporting documentation.

I understand that the Fellowship does not create any employment relationship with RESILIENCE or the TNA Host Institution(s). I am solely responsible for any tax, insurance, or social security obligations arising from the award.

TNA Fellow Rights

As a TNA Fellow I am entitled to:

- Free access to the collections and facilities of the host institution(s), including a free workspace.
- Request a meeting with (an) expert(s) in my field at the host institution(s);
- Request to present my research at the host institution(s), subject to feasibility and institutional capacity.
- Be contacted by a representative of the host institution(s) to help facilitate the visit.

TNA Fellow Obligations

As a TNA Fellow I undertake to:

- Communicate with the host institution(s) regarding my stay and access needs, e.g., specific collections/material, guidance from archival staff, access to research expertise;
- Comply with rules and regulations of the host institution(s) and conform with the law of the host country in which the host institution(s) are located;
- Arrange my own insurance to cover healthcare, travel and liability insurance with adequate cover for the whole duration of the Fellowship;
- where feasible, present their research at the host institution (unless this proves unpractical or difficult, e.g., because the fellowship is too short or takes place during the summer months)

- Where feasible provide RESILIENCE with dissemination materials about my Fellowship (blogs, articles, pictures, testimonies, etc.);
- Complete the TNA report and evaluation no later than 6 weeks after the end of their fellowship;
- Complete the TNA evaluation form 12 months after the end of their fellowship;
- Inform RESILIENCE TNA and the host institution of research outputs from the Fellowship once published (including but not limited to: academic articles, conference presentations, datasets, databases, scientific communication). The following statement should be used: "Research for this project was made possible through the support of the RESILIENCE TNA Fellowship Programme taken at [name of host institution]."

Finally, I acknowledge that I am encouraged to join the RESILIENCE TNA Fellow Alumni Network.

Withdrawal and Non-Compliance

I understand that failure to meet the obligations of the Fellowship, including early cancellation or failure to participate, may result in RESILIENCE to withdraw the Fellowship award and requesting full or partial reimbursement of the allowance paid.

Date and Signature TNA Fellow

Name:

Place:

Date:

Signature:

Data Protection

RESILIENCE sets out to only collect and keep as much and as long personal data from its users as is necessary for the attainment of the specific purpose for which the data is collected and will not communicate these personal data to a third-party unless there is a legal obligation to do so.

7.5 TNA Fellow Financial Guidance

Financial Guidance for the RESILIENCE TNA Fellowship Programme

RESILIENCE offers recipients of a TNA fellowship (1) reimbursement of travel costs from the fellow's usual place of residence to the host institution and (2) an accommodation or accommodation allowance and (3) a subsistence allowance during the fellow's stay at the host institution. Rates are subject to review and might change. The following guidance applies.

Guidance on reimbursement of travel costs

- Travel costs will be reimbursed based on the most appropriate and cost-effective means of transport from the fellow's country of residence to the host country.
- Eligible travel costs include costs for long distance travel between countries and travel costs from and to the airport/train or bus station, in both the host country and the country of residence.
- Travel to and from countries other than the host country and the fellow's country of residence needs to be justified. RESILIENCE will decide on the amount and eligibility of these costs for reimbursement of these travel expenses.
- Only economy (2nd class) tickets of flights and trains are reimbursed. Other tickets are reimbursed to the level of the economy fare.
- Costs for seat reservation, transport of necessary luggage and supplements for fast trains are eligible expenses.
- Reimbursement ceiling for direct flights in Europe is €400.
- Reimbursement ceiling for flights outside of Europe is €800.
- Flights with higher costs are only reimbursed with prior approval by RESILIENCE.
- Taxi expenses are usually not reimbursed. In exceptional cases, costs might be reimbursed if proof is provided that the expense was reasonable and explicitly motivated, e.g., when no public transport is available or for early departure (between 0.00 am and 7.00 am) and/or late arrivals (after 10.00pm), usually only up to a maximum of 40 EUR per leg. Taxi receipts are always required.
- Local transport costs between the accommodation and the host institution must be covered from the subsistence allowance.
- Car rental is not reimbursed. Costs for travel by private car are also eligible provided the shortest route is taken. Reimbursement may be claimed at €0,23 cents/km for the roundtrip up to a

maximum of €400. Additional accommodation while travelling by car is not eligible for reimbursement.

How to claim reimbursement for travel costs

- The RESILIENCE reimbursement form must be submitted to RESILIENCE no later than 1 month after the end of the fellowship.
- The reimbursement form must be accompanied by the original invoices, boarding cards and flight tickets.

Weighted total grant per country

RESILIENCE contributes towards accommodation and subsistence costs during the fellow’s stay at the host institution using fixed rates that are weighted by country⁴⁴. Fellows do not need to provide proof of costs via receipts etc. The table below shows the total grant available as weighted per country. The travel costs are deducted from this total, and the remainder of the grant is paid in EUROS to the TNA Fellow at the start of the fellowship.

Country	RESILIENCE Full Grant in EUR
Albania	1338
Belgium	2000
Bosnia and Herzegovina	1218
Bulgaria	1212
Czechia	1564
France	2064
Germany	2000
Greece	1622
Israel	2180
Italy	1724
Netherlands	2198
Slovenia	1598

⁴⁴ Countries listed are possible locations of RESILIENCE Host institutions. Rates are based on Eurostat correction coefficients [in the EU](#) and [outside of the EU](#) as of 2024.

7.6 TNA Fellow Online Application Form

(The TNA Fellow Online Application Form is being submitted online and is only available during the opening of a call for applications.)

Application Form RESILIENCE TNA

About You

Name (Required)

Email (Required)

Confirm email (Required)

Institution (Required)

Country (Required)

Gender (Required)

Female

Male

Non-binary / Third gender

Prefer not to say

Other

What is your academic position? (Required)

Student

PhD candidate

Postdoctoral researcher

Research associate

Assistant Professor

Associate Professor

Full Professor

Librarian / Archivist

Other

How familiar you are with the research infrastructure RESILIENCE? (Required)

Not at all

Minimally

Moderately well

Very well

Your CV

Your CV (Required)

Upload here your CV in .pdf or .docx format.

Accepted file types: pdf, docx, Max. file size: 128 MB.

Relevant Publications

Relevant Publications (Required)

Indicate here your most important publications for the project (max. 5). If there no relevant publications yet, list relevant thesis and name of promotor.

Planned Publications

Planned Publications (Required)

Indicate here your planned publications as a result of your stay at the TNA host insitution.

Required Material

Required Material (collections, objects, etc) (Required)

Indicate here your wishes regarding material you want to use for your research.

Duration and Period

Write here an indication of the duration for access (typically two weeks) and the desired period for access.

Starting Date, please enter a date from [date] (Required)

MM slash DD slash YYYY

End Date (Required)

MM slash DD slash YYYY

TNA Host

TNA Host (Required)

Indicate here the name of the TNA Host you would like to visit.

Fscire

Archivio Generale Arcivescovile di Bologna, AAB

Bar-Ilan University

Bektashi World Center

Bibliothèque nationale et universitaire de Strasbourg

CIRCSE

École Pratique des Hautes Études

ITSERR

J.A. Comenius Museum, Uherský Brod

KU Leuven

New Georgian University "Saint Epiphanos"

Cultural Academy Cyprus

Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski"

Theological University of Apeldoorn

University of Münster

University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Theology

University of Sarajevo

Volos Academy for Theological Studies

Abstract of Your Project

Abstract of Your Project (Required)

Please enter here an abstract of your project (max. 500 characters). Include the following: your research question and current state of the art, methodology, and expected aims and outcomes

0 of 500 max characters

Description of Your Project

Description of Your Project (Required)

Please upload here an extended presentation of your project (max. 6.000 characters), making reference to relevant criteria in the TNA call.

Accepted file types: pdf, docx, ppt, Max. file size: 128 MB.

Relevance of Your Project

Describe here in max. 500 characters the relevance of your project for RESILIENCE.

0 of 500 max characters

Where did you first hear or read about the call for TNA fellowships?

Tell us where you first heard or read the news about this call (Required)

RESILIENCE Newsletter

Other newsletter (specify below)

RESILIENCE website

Other website (specify below)

RESILIENCE press release

Personal contact with a RESILIENCE affiliate.

Personal contact with an affiliate of my institution.

Personal contact with another person.

Social Media (specify below)

Flyer

Other (specify below)

Conditions (Required)

I have read and I understand the condition: "Unless otherwise indicated on the webpages of the TNA hosts, there is no financial support nor any assistance in finding lodging from the side of RESILIENCE nor from the side of the TNA host."

Permission (Required)

I give permission for my name and the title of the project to be published on the RESILIENCE website if my application is successful.

Message

Let us know your questions, remarks, feedback etc. (Required)

Let us know your questions, remarks, feedback etc.

Consent (Required)

I agree to the privacy policy.

7.8 TNA Fellow Invitation

Invitation for a RESILIENCE TNA Fellowship

[date], [location]

To whom it may concern

TNA Fellow: [Title] [Name] [Institute of origin]

TNA Host: [Name centre/archive if relevant], [Name TNA Host]

This is to certify that [Name TNA Scholar] has been awarded a fellowship to pursue academic research at the [name TNA Host], within the frame of the EU ESFRI research infrastructure RESILIENCE, which offers Transnational Access to Special Collections and Archival Documents within the field of religious studies. [Name] has specified a research program which [short description research]. He/She is therefore warmly invited to spend [length of stay] at [TNA Host] to conduct research in their libraries and collections, as well as meet experts. His/Her stay in [TNA Host] is planned from **[Exact Dates Research Stay]**. The RESILIENCE TNA fellowship program provides free access to the institution and the required collections, a place to work, as well as ensuring contact with relevant experts during the visit.

TNA coordinator and point of contact at [TNA Host]

[Name TNA Coordinator], [Email TNA Coordinator]

About RESILIENCE

RESILIENCE is a unique, interdisciplinary and invigorating research infrastructure for Religious Studies, building a high-performance platform, supplying evolving tools and big data to scholars from all the scientific disciplines crossing religions in their diachronical and synchronical variety.

The ESFRI Forum included RESILIENCE in its 2021 Roadmap, placing it in the strategic framework for Research Infrastructures in the European Research Area. RESILIENCE Preparatory Phase Project (2022-2026) is funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No 101079792.

Contact: tna_scholar@resilience-ri.eu

7.9 TNA Fellow Evaluation Form

The TNA Fellow Evaluation Form was developed in 2022. It can be accessed online here:

[TNA Fellow Evaluation Form](#)

7.10 TNA Fellow Certificate

CERTIFICATE OF FELLOWSHIP for Transnational Access

This is to certify that

was awarded a RESILIENCE TNA Fellowship

at

from to

to conduct research on the research project:

The fellowship offered access to sources, documents, manuscripts, rare books, resources, instruments, files and databases available through the TNA Host, combined with direct contact with experts in the field of research.

Description of work:

The workload amounted to about hours within this period.

Date:

Signature:

Name:

CERTIFICATE

7.11 TNA Communication Strategy Frame

Communication Strategy Frame TNA Programme 03.00

8 Applicable Documents

Applicable documents are documents from which all requirements must be fulfilled in the context of the Grant Agreement, although they are not repeated in the present document.

ID	Date	Title/Reference
A1	28/08/2022	Grant Agreement 101079792

9 Reference Documents

Reference documents are intended to provide background and supplementary information.

ID	Date	Title/Reference
R1	02/08/2024	RESILIENCE WP1 D1.3 FSP FinancialSustainabilityPlan_01.00_FINAL
R2	24/07/2025	RESILIENCE WP2 D2.1 Services Preparation and Implementation Strategy_03.00_FINAL
R3	29/02/2024	RESILIENCE WP3 D3.1 WorkshopProceedings1_01.00_FINAL
R4	31/10/2023	RESILIENCE WP3 D3.5 User Stories Catalogue - 1st Batch_01.00_FINAL
R5	21/11/2024	RESILIENCE WP4 D4.2 CDEP_01.00_FINAL
R6	23/12/2022	RESILIENCE WP6 D6.3 DetailedOrganisationalPlan_01.00_FINAL

Funded by
the European Union

[end of document]